

Reactions of Silicon Alkoxides with Phthalic and Succinic Anhydrides

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Reactions of ethyl orthosilicate and isopropyl orthosilicate with phthalic and succinic anhydrides show that the reaction in 1:1 molar ratio affords the trialkoxy monophthalate or trialkoxy monosuccinate derivatives, but when the alkoxides and acid anhydrides are taken in molar ratio of 1:2, the end product is always dialkoxysilicon diphthalate or disuccinate derivative.

The reaction of alkyl orthosilicate with acetic anhydride was studied by Friedel and Crafts¹ and by Post and Hofrichter². The reaction between ethyl orthosilicate and a dibasic acid anhydride was tried for the first time by Dearing and Reid³ who attempted the reaction by heating ethyl orthosilicate with one mole of phthalic anhydride for 8 hours at 160°. According to these workers, ethyl phthalate formed was separated by fractionation in vacuum and identified by boiling point, density, and saponification number; the other product was assumed to be diethyl silicate, although this could not be identified. The reaction can therefore be represented as:

It therefore appears that the above workers failed to obtain any alkoxysilicon acylate with phthalic anhydride and even the silicon compound obtained could not be identified.

The present workers have studied the reaction between silicon alkoxides, both with monobasic and dibasic acid anhydrides. In a recent communication⁴ on the reaction between silicon alkoxides and aliphatic monobasic acid anhydrides, it was shown that when the above reactants were mixed in equimolar ratios, the products formed were always trialkoxysilicon monoacylates, but with larger proportions of the acid anhydride, the products were always dialkoxysilicon diacylates.

The present study has been extended to dibasic acid anhydrides. The reactions in molar ratio of 1:1 or 1:2 (or greater than 1:2) could be represented by the following equations:

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1866 iv, 9, 10.
2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 443.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 3058.
4. Narain and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 855.

Thus like a monobasic acid anhydride, phthalic or succinic anhydride in its reaction with ethyl orthosilicate or isopropyl orthosilicate afforded a trialkoxysilicon monophthalate or monosuccinate ester when taken in molar ratio of 1:1, but when the alkoxide and acid anhydride were taken in 1:2 or 1:4 molar ratio, the products were always dialkoxysilicon diacylate esters.

The reactions with dibasic acid anhydrides are very slow and even after long refluxing (about 50 hr.), only 40% yields of the product could be obtained. It was confirmed that the rest of the reactants remained unchanged.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Filtrations were done in a specially fabricated apparatus in which contact with moisture was excluded.

Silicon ethoxide was an E. Merck sample and freshly distilled before use and confirmed by estimation of silicon and ethoxyl contents.

Silicon isopropoxide was prepared by the method of Ridge and Todd⁵ and confirmed by its boiling point and analysis of the silicon content.

Phthalic anhydride was an E. Merck sample. Succinic anhydride was prepared by refluxing for an hour succinic acid (29.0 g.) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (51.0 g.) in an oil bath (115°) with occasional shaking. When the contents had become a clear solution, the refluxing was continued further for an hour to ensure completeness of the reaction. Then it was cooled and left overnight, when a white crystalline substance appeared. It was washed first with a little benzene and then with dry ether, and finally dried under pump at about 35°/2 mm for about 2 hr.; yield 21.5 g., m.p. 119-20°.

Silicon was estimated by digestion of the compound with a small amount of H₂SO₄ (conc.), followed by addition of a few drops of HNO₃ (conc.) and slow ignition to the dioxide.

TABLE I
 Reactions of silicon alkoxides with phthalic and succinic anhydrides.

No.	Reactants. Molar ratio.		Reflux period.	Uchanged acid anhydride filtered.	Drying condi- tions.	Product and yield after ether washing and drying.	M.P.	% Silicon.		% Alkoxy.	
	a	b						Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	3.27 g.	1 : 1	5½ hr.	1.58 g. 1½ hr.	50°/2 mm for 1½ hr.	Reaction between (a) Si(OEt) ₄ and (b) C ₆ H ₄ (CO) ₂ O.	110°	7.78	7.85	37.70	37.92
	2.20										
2	3.53	1 : 2	4	4.00	50°/2 mm for 1 hr.	(EtO) ₃ Si(OOC.C ₆ H ₄ .CO ₂ Et) (1.35 g.)	125°	5.50	5.55	17.80	17.85
	4.92										
3	4.00	1 : 4	4	10.50	45°/3 mm for 1 hr.	(EtO) ₃ Si(OOC.C ₆ H ₄ .CO ₂ Et) ₂ (1.0 g.)	125°	5.50	5.55	17.50	17.85
	11.36										
4	2.77	1 : 1	5½	0.98	48°/3.5 mm for 1½ hr.	Reaction between (a) Si(OPr) ₄ and (b) C ₆ H ₄ (CO) ₂ O.	138°	6.81	6.78	..	..
	1.50										
5	4.09	1 : 2	5	3.00	50°/2 mm for 1 hr.	(OPr) ₃ Si(OOC.C ₆ H ₄ .CO ₂ Pr) ₂ (0.03 g.)	126.5°	5.07	5.00	..	..
	4.80										
6	4.30	1 : 4	4	9.00	55°/5 mm for 1½ hr.	(OPr) ₃ Si(OOC.C ₆ H ₄ .CO ₂ .Pr) ₂ (1.8g.)	126.5°	5.68	5.00	..	..
	9.96										
7	2.25	1 : 1	5½	0.80	55°/2 mm for 1 hr.	Reaction between Si (a) (OEt) ₄ and (b) C ₆ H ₄ (CO) ₂ O.	126°	8.99	9.08	..	..
	1.06										
8	2.04	1 : 2	24	1.22	50°/5 mm for 1 hr.	(OEt) ₃ Si(OOC.(CH ₂) ₄ .COOEt) (0.48)	113°	6.89	6.86	22.04	22.05
	1.94										
9	1.35	1 : 1	51	0.25	40°/2 mm for 1 hr.	Reaction between (a) Si(OPr) ₄ and (b) C ₆ H ₄ (CO) ₂ O.	115°	7.68	7.60	..	..
	0.53										
10	2.24	1 : 2	11	1.28	45°/3 mm for 1 hr.	(OPr) ₃ Si(OOC.(CH ₂) ₄ .COOPr) (0.58g.)	..	6.02	6.03	..	..
	1.63										

N. B. Product obtained in each case was a white solid.

The ethoxide and isopropoxide were estimated by oxidation of a small definite amount of the compound with $N\text{-K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (in 12.5% H_2SO_4 and after allowing it to stand for 2 hr. at the room temperature, the unused chromic acid was titrated iodometrically. Methods of preparation being similar, details are recorded for one preparation only.

Reaction between $\text{Si}(\text{OEt})_4$ and C_6H_4 O in dry Benzene in Molar Ratio 1:1.—

To silicon ethoxide (3.27 g.) was added phthalic anhydride (2.2 g.), followed by dry benzene (20.5 g.). No heat was liberated and phthalic anhydride settled at the bottom. The contents were shaken and refluxed for 5½ hr. between 110° and 120° with periodical shaking to ensure thorough reaction. It was then cooled and filtered under vacuum, when a white solid residue (1.06 g., m.p. 128-29°) having practically neither silicon nor ethoxyl was obtained. The clear filtrate was left overnight when again a little white deposit (0.5 g.) was formed. The clear supernatant liquid was carefully filtered. This white substance, thus crystallised on drying in vacuum, showed very little, practically negligible, silicon and ethoxyl.

When the supernatant liquid, containing benzene, was dried under pump, immediately a white crystalline substance started appearing. When almost all the benzene had been removed, it was dried under pump at bath 50°/2 mm for about 1¼ hr. A little colorless liquid did not, however, appear to volatilise under these conditions. The contents were then washed thrice with dry ether (ca. 4 ml at a time) and again dried under pump at 50° bath for 1 hr. when a white crystalline substance (1.35 g., m.p. 110°) was obtained. [Found: Si, 7.78; OEt, 37.70; $(\text{EtO})_3\text{Si}(\text{OCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CO}_2\text{Et})$ requires Si, 7.85; OEt, 37.92%].

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